

Thermal Shrinking of Biopolymeric Hydrogels for High Resolution 3D Printing of Kidney Tubules

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The effective replication of microtubular structures in tissue engineering remains a great challenge. In this study, the temperature-responsive characteristics of poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM) to create intricate, high-resolution tubular structures through a shrinking mechanism is investigated by exploring 2 thermosensitive hydrogels—gelatin methacryloyl (gelMA) and silk fibroin methacryloyl (silkMA)—combined with pNIPAM. Systematic investigations revealed precise control of shrinking behavior at elevated temperatures (33–37 °C) as a function of polymer concentration. The hydrogel sizes reduce by $\approx 15\%$ from room temperature (RT) to 33 °C and $\approx 40\%$ from RT to 37 °C for both hydrogel types. The shrinking affects the mechanical properties, increasing the compressive modulus by ≈ 2.8 -fold for gelMA-pNIPAM gels and ≈ 5.1 -fold for silkMA-pNIPAM gels at 37 °C. Combined with volumetric printing, these materials achieve resolution enhancements of $\approx 20\%$ for positive features and $\approx 70\%$ for negative features, enabling the creation of complex, high-resolution structures within seconds, with open channels ($\approx 50 \mu\text{m}$). GelMA-pNIPAM hydrogels show better cell compatibility compared to silkMA-pNIPAM hydrogels, promoting cell adhesion and viability. This study demonstrates the thermosensitive hydrogels' capability to engineer intricate, high-resolution tubular structures with volumetric printing—an efficient route to fabricate microenvironments mimicking native tissues with potential for developing relevant *in vitro* models.

1. Introduction

The systemic balance of the body relies on the continuous exchange of molecules among organs, facilitated by intricate tubular networks. These networks span various length scales, from large diameters in organs like the intestine to microscale capillaries in tissues like the kidneys, where approximately one million nephrons intricately transport nutrients and waste.^[1–3]

Reproducing the scale of these microtubular features may be key for engineering functional (kidney) tissue constructs.^[4–6] Several methods have been explored to create tubular structures in engineered tissues. These approaches typically involve cellular self-assembly to drive tubulogenesis^[7] or biomaterial-based techniques with the necessary physical and chemical cues to support tube formation by cultured cells.^[7] Among the latter, commonly used strategies include 3D printing with sacrificial materials^[8] or cell-laden bioinks^[9] and light-mediated 3D printing.^[4,10] However, the working principle of these printing approaches is extremely time-consuming, generally yielding only a few units over

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several hours, which poses a significant challenge when attempting to scale up to clinically relevant quantities. Furthermore, the existing library of hydrogel materials compatible with such techniques is still rather limited, especially those that support cellular function,^[11–13] making tubular structures difficult to manipulate and limiting their practical applications.^[5] Although significant progress has been made,^[14] there is still a need for a better method to create micron-scale tubular structures in engineered tissues. In this context, stimuli-responsive hydrogels, such as gels based on poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM), offer a solution by undergoing rapid volume changes in response to temperature changes.^[15–18] PNIPAM exhibits lower critical solution temperature (LCST) behavior ≈ 32 °C in water.^[18–20] Above this temperature, it undergoes conformational changes, leading to decreased solubility and wettability, while below the LCST, it reverts to its hydrated form.^[21–23]

PNIPAM's ability to expel water at temperatures above its LCST has been utilized to create tubular structures in a microfluidic system,^[20–24] reducing vessel wall size and increasing channel diameter, mimicking vasodilation.^[20] Another technology utilized pNIPAM to shrink simple tubular structures made of hydrogels and sacrificial materials, resulting in shrunken structures with high cell viability over 7 days.^[25]

In this study, we capitalized on pNIPAM's shrinking properties and employed volumetric printing to fabricate intricate tubular structures mimicking kidney tissue. While other printing methods such as multi-photon laser ablation^[26–29] or digital light processing^[30] have achieved open channels in the range of tens of micrometers using biocompatible hydrogels, their limitations include the time required to print large clinically relevant sized structures for in vitro modeling or potential implantation.

Volumetric printing (VP) enables rapid, layerless 3D printing of complex structures within seconds.^[31] By projecting light encoded with the object's design onto a rotating vial of photosensitive resin, VP achieves precise, localized solidification of the desired regions through covalent crosslinking.^[31] This method offers high design flexibility and can process various photoreponsive hydrogels,^[32] theoretically achieving resolutions down to 27 μm .^[32,33] However, the resolution may be affected by factors such as light sources and material properties, especially when printing intricate features like pores and channels.^[32,34] While multi-material printing and controlled cell patterning have been demonstrated,^[34–37] the use of smart, stimuli-responsive bio resins in VP remains still limited.^[32]

Herein, the novel VP approach and the shrinking capabilities of pNIPAM-based materials are converged to fabricate freeform, high-resolution microscale tubular structures. As printable resins, we developed biopolymeric hydrogels with methacryloyl moieties, either gelatin methacryloyl (gelMA) or silk fibroin methacryloyl (silkMA), which were combined with NIPAM monomers to introduce thermosensitivity in the printable materials.

The hydrogel precursor solutions (either gelMA or silkMA) mixed with NIPAM have been transformed into 3D polymer networks through light-induced radical polymerization, in which pNIPAM connects the gelMA or silkMA biopolymeric chains. The shrinking capacity of the resulting hydrogels was investigated upon exposure to 37 °C (as shown in the schematic overview reported in **Figure 1**).

Our goal was to achieve 3D structures with shape and size comparable to the kidney proximal tubule (diameter ≈ 30 – 40 μm) by combining the temperature-sensitive shrinking capacity of gelMA-pNIPAM or silkMA-pNIPAM hydrogels with the volumetric 3D printer (**Figure 1B**).^[31] Furthermore, as a proof-of-concept for biological applications, we investigated the growth and maturation of proximal tubule (PT) kidney cells on these materials by visualization of the formation of cell mono-layers along the inner wall of the artificial tubules (**Figure 1C**).

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Material Characterization

The temperature response and the influence of gelMA on the thermoresponsive properties of pNIPAM hydrogels have recently been investigated by Li et al.^[25] They extensively examined the relationship between gelMA and pNIPAM and its impact on the shrinking process. Noteworthy is that both pNIPAM and gelatin display temperature-dependent behavior, but in an opposite manner. PNIPAM has a distinct LCST transition, while gelMA's temperature sensitivity is associated with gradual gelation upon decreasing temperature rather than a sharp phase transition or clear volume change. Therefore, the pNIPAM fraction of the materials dominates the shrinking properties.

This study demonstrated good shrinking of tube structures and excellent results in vitro and in vivo. Nevertheless, this demonstration was limited to a single hydrogel composition and simple tube structures. Taking into consideration these findings, we sought to demonstrate the versatility of the shrinking effect, irrespective of the chosen biopolymer. Therefore, we explored silk fibroin as an additional biopolymer of interest, given its promising applications in biofabrication research.^[38] Similar to gelatin, silk fibroin possesses side groups on its polymer chain (attributed to the presence of tyrosine and serine and a limited amount of other reactive amino acid residues), which allow for functionalization. The methacrylation of silk fibroin, a process optimized by Kim et al.,^[39] was assessed by proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H-NMR). In particular, the vinyl group ($\delta = 6.2$ – 6 and 5.8 – 5.6 ppm) and the methyl group of the introduced methacryloyl moiety (MA) at $\delta = 1.8$ ppm were detected after reaction with glycidyl methacrylate (GMA). It is important to note the disparity in the degree of methacrylation between gelatin and silk fibroin. It is well established that gelatin possesses a large amount of reactive functional groups within its side chains, which allow the level of functionalization to be adjusted as needed.^[40] In contrast, silk fibroin is composed mainly of glycine and alanine residues, which lack reactive side groups, and only a modest percentage of serine ($\approx 12\%$).^[41] As a result, the functionalization potential of silk fibroin is more limited than that of gelatin, which was also confirmed by ¹H-NMR making use of an internal standard showing a degree of methacrylation (DoM) of 0.27 mmol g⁻¹ for gelMA and 0.13 mmol g⁻¹ for silkMA (**Figure S1**, Supporting Information).

First, a concentration screening was conducted to investigate the shrinking properties of gelMA- and silkMA-pNIPAM-based hydrogels. Previous research has emphasized the importance of achieving an optimal shrinking capacity through a delicate balance between water content and polymer concentration within

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the overall process: A) Chemical composition of the 2 hydrogels gelMA-pNIPAM or silkMA-pNIPAM; B) Overview of the tomographic volumetric printing process; C) Cell seeding using human conditionally immortalized proximal tubule epithelial cells (ciPTECs) inside hollow tubules printed with the tomographic volumetric printer in gelMA-pNIPAM or silkMA-pNIPAM hydrogels.

A. Influence of total polymer concentration on shrinking efficacy

B. Formulation influence on shrinking efficacy

C. Photocrosslinking

D. Sol fraction

sol fraction day 1	
SilkMA-pNIPAM	29 ± 13%
SilkMA	11 ± 14%
GelMA-pNIPAM	15 ± 9%
GelMA	7 ± 6%

Figure 2. A) Effect of total polymer concentration on the shrinking of GelMA-pNIPAM cylindrically shaped hydrogels with an initial diameter of 12 mm. The GelMA concentration was kept constant at 2.5% and the NIPAM concentration was varied from 2.5% to 12.5% ($n = 3$); B) Biopolymer-pNIPAM ratio influence on the shrinking capacity of the hydrogels over 24 h (starting diameter 8 mm; Temperature before shrinking 25 °C; temperature after shrinking 37 °C) C. Crosslinking kinetics of silkMA-pNIPAM and gelMA-pNIPAM hydrogels compared with the relative non-thermosensitive control groups ($n = 3$) at 25 °C; D. Sol fraction values of the silkMA-pNIPAM, silkMA, gelMA-pNIPAM and gelMA hydrogels.

the hydrogel.^[42,43] Here, 2 experiments were conducted, first, the biopolymer concentration (GelMA and SilkMA) was kept constant at 2.5 wt.%, which corresponds to the lowest possible concentration ensuring stable gelMA- or silkMA-gel formation. **Figure 2A** shows the effect of variations in NIPAM monomer concentration on shrinking upon elevated temperatures, measured as the decrease of the diameter of cylindrical-shaped hydrogels. As pNIPAM is needed to induce shrinking, we observed more efficient shrinking with increasing NIPAM content. However, an optimum was reached at 10% NIPAM and a further increase in NIPAM concentration led to less efficient shrinking. Previously, shrinking materials based on electrostatic interactions showed that shrinking efficiency was negatively correlated to the total polymer concentration.^[44] Clearly, at a higher initial water content, more water can be expelled upon the shrinking trigger, which is likely also related to a less dense and therefore more flexible polymer network enabling shape reduction. Since the most efficient shrinking effect was observed at a total polymer concentration of 10 wt.%, this concentration was kept constant throughout all subsequent experiments.

A second experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of the biopolymer/NIPAM ratio, the shrinking of disk-shaped hydrogels with an initial diameter of 8 mm was investigated for both compositions (gelMA-NIPAM and silkMA-NIPAM) at the following ratios of biopolymer-NIPAM: 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, and 1:5, while keeping the overall concentration at 10 wt.% (Figure 2B). The hydrogels were incubated at 37 °C and their size was monitored measuring the diameter. Over 24 h, it was observed that increasing the NIPAM content in the hydrogel precursor solution resulted in a more pronounced shrinking effect, reaching

its maximum at a ratio of 1:4. This led to a diameter decrease ranging from 25% to 40% for both silkMA and gelMA-based hydrogels, depending on the ratios. At higher relative NIPAM content, no further shrinking was observed. Notably, there was no difference in the extent of shrinking between silkMA-pNIPAM and gelMA-pNIPAM, indicating that the slight difference in DoM and thus crosslink density for both systems do not significantly affect the shrinking extent and that both biopolymers serve as suitable foundations for thermally shrinking materials. Consequently, a 1:4 ratio was selected for all subsequent experiments to maximize the shrinking capacity.

As the next step in characterizing the different materials, rheology measurements were conducted to investigate the gelation kinetics of silkMA-NIPAM and gelMA-NIPAM precursor solutions. Since all the gels in this study were prepared at 25 °C, we decided to keep this temperature constant also for all the rheology experiments. Figure 2C illustrates that both biopolymers combined with NIPAM and their respective controls (silkMA or gelMA alone) rapidly formed a polymer network upon UV light illumination, reaching the maximum storage modulus within a few seconds. The final storage modulus values exhibited similar trends between silkMA-pNIPAM, gelMA-pNIPAM, and their controls. Specifically, for silkMA-pNIPAM and silkMA, the values of G' were 108 ± 38 Pa and 307 ± 57 Pa, respectively. On the other hand, for gelMA-pNIPAM and gelMA, the values of G' were 243 ± 116 Pa and 1326 ± 56 Pa, respectively. All gels were shape-stable and could be easily handled and removed from their molds. The difference in the G' values between the biopolymer-pNIPAM and the biopolymerMA is related to the higher concentration of biopolymer in the controls (not containing NIPAM).

A. Shrinking kinetics

B. Mechanical properties

i.

Volume [mm ³]	25°C	33°C	37°C
SilkMA-pNIPAM	179.1±4.7	89.6±6.7	42.9±1.9
SilkMA	192.0±10.7	235.2±38.7	214.8±17.1
GelMA-pNIPAM	165.6±31.7	114.6±7.7	49.0±4.8
GelMA	183.5±22.7	176.1±8.6	226.9±34.8

SilkMA
 GelMA
 SilkMA-pNIPAM
 GelMA-pNIPAM

Figure 3. A) *i*) Shrinking kinetics evaluation of silkMA-pNIPAM, gelMA-pNIPAM, and the relative nonthermosensitive controls. Images at 25 °C were taken immediately after the gel formation, images at 33 and 37 °C were taken after 24 h in PBS (scale bar = 0.5 cm); *ii*), change in gel diameter in the first 3 h of incubation ($n = 3$). B) *i*). Volume calculation at 25, 33, and 37 °C ($n = 3$) – samples used for Young's modulus analysis (samples at 25 °C measured immediately after the gel formation, samples at 33 and 37 °C measured after a week of incubation); *ii*) Young's modulus of silkMA-pNIPAM and gelMA-pNIPAM hydrogels compared with the relative control groups ($n = 3$). (* = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$).

Furthermore, for controls, each MA group participates in crosslinking while in NIPAM-containing solutions only the acrylamide groups connecting to biopolymerMA participate in crosslinking, while most NIPAM monomers contribute to linear pNIPAM chains within the network. These linear pNIPAM chains do not contribute to additional network branches.

Figure 2D shows the values of mass loss at day 1 (sol fraction) of the different hydrogels, silkMA-pNIPAM, silkMA, gelMA-pNIPAM, and gelMA, respectively. These measurements represent the photocrosslinking efficacy of the different hydrogel precursor solutions.^[45–47] The pNIPAM-based hydrogels showed a higher sol fraction than silkMA and gelMA, aligning with the previous discussion on the values of the storage moduli (G'). The highest mass loss can also be visually observed, as water in which pNIPAM-based gels are incubated turns slightly white after one day of incubation. This shows that some pNIPAM oligomers are expelled from the hydrogel in the shrinking process (Figure S6, Supporting Information).

To evaluate the shrinking kinetics of disk-shaped hydrogels, gelMA-pNIPAM, silkMA-pNIPAM, and their respective non-thermosensitive controls were incubated at 33 and 37 °C. Photographs were taken at 10-min intervals for 1 h, followed by additional images at 2 and 24 h, and the diameters were measured. Figure 3A(i) presents images of the hydrogels at 3 stages: immediately after crosslinking (temperature controlled) at 25 °C, and after one week of incubation at 33 and 37 °C. Most of the shrinking occurred within the first hour of incubation, and the hydrogel size remained relatively stable thereafter (Figure 3A(ii)), this shrinking was calculated based on the decrease in diameter of cylindrically shaped hydrogels (as seen in Figure 3A(i)), however is worth to mention that the observed shrinking is proportional in all directions. Overall, we observed a shrinkage of $\approx 25\%$ at 33 °C for both compositions; and a shrinking of 35% and 40% at 37 °C for gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM hydrogels, respectively.

Comparing the shrinking of the 2 hydrogels at the 2 temperatures, we observed an increase of $\approx 10\%$ – 15% in

shrinking from 33 to 37 °C, proving that increasing temperature relates to a greater shrinking extent of the hydrogel, as previously reported.^[48] Although the formation of crystalline regions in silk polymer chains may result in further shrinking effects, these effects seemed negligible and no significant further reduction in sizes was observed over 28 days. Moreover, we noted a complete reversibility of the shrinkage effect. This feature can be a double-edged weapon, as on one hand it allows considerable versatility of the gels but on the other makes characterization techniques (such as imaging) more challenging with the need for stable temperature maintenance.

After measuring the volume change upon complete shrinking, the estimated water content for the 10 wt.% gels (ratio biopolymer to NIPAm 1:4) decreased to ≈63% assuming that all NIPAm monomers were incorporated. However, Figure S6 (Supporting Information) reveals a slight initial outflow of pNIPAM oligomers from the gel during the first few hours of shrinking. This suggests that the actual water content may be higher than the calculated 63%, potentially altering the biopolymer to pNIPAM ratio slightly.

In general, changes in mechanical properties can affect cell behavior and therefore it is important to assess the impact of water expulsion on the stiffness of hydrogels. Uniaxial compression tests were performed to assess the effect of shrinking on the mechanical properties (Figure S3, Supporting Information). Figure 3B(i) presents the initial volumes of the gels prior to mechanical testing. Notably, distinct behavior was observed between gels containing and not containing pNIPAM. The gelMA and silkMA controls, incubated in PBS at 33 or 37 °C, exhibited swelling, resulting in decreased stiffness as evident from the compression tests (Figure 3B(ii)). The compression modulus was reduced ≈1.4- and 1.2-fold from 25 to 33 °C and 1.8 and 1.3-fold from 33 to 37 °C for gelMA and silkMA, respectively. Consequently, there was an overall decline in compression modulus of ≈2.6-fold for gelMA and 1.5-fold for silkMA, spanning the temperature range from 25 to 37 °C.

In contrast, hydrogels containing pNIPAM exhibited a reduction in volume upon incubation (Figure 3B(i)), leading to water expulsion and subsequent increase in the compression modulus. Specifically, the gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM gels demonstrated ≈1.8- and 1.6-fold increase in compression modulus from 25 to 33 °C and 1.5- and 3.1-fold increase from 33 to 37 °C, respectively. Accordingly, there was a total increase in compression modulus of ≈2.8-fold for gelMA-pNIPAM and 5.1-fold for silkMA-pNIPAM, spanning the temperature range from 25 to 37 °C (Figure 3B(ii)). This behavior was to be expected, as the ejection of water due to shrinking instigates a concomitant contraction of the polymer network, thereby leading to an enhancement in the rigidity of the gel, aligning with previously reported findings.^[43,49]

2.2. Volumetric printing

A thermally controlled shrinking behavior brings several opportunities when it comes to the 3D printing of microchannels, as a potential, materials-driven approach to achieve high-resolution structures that better mimic native tissue features. The recently introduced VP approach allows for single-step printing of large

and complex architectures in a matter of seconds.^[31] Figure 4 shows the VP prints of silkMA-pNIPAM and gelMA-pNIPAM designed in star shapes and open channels. Both VP-printed silkMA-pNIPAM and gelMA-pNIPAM structures demonstrated significant resolution enhancement for both positive and negative features upon thermally-induced shrinking, which was calculated as the decrease in the width of the tip of a star (for positive figures) and as the decrease in the diameter of the central channel (for negative figures). The scaffold made with SilkMA-pNIPAM hydrogel showed a significant resolution enhancement of ≈26% for simple positive (from $\approx 36.7 \pm 1.8 \mu\text{m}$ to $\approx 27.0 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{m}$), and of ≈67% for negative features (from $\approx 220.3 \pm 2.4 \mu\text{m}$ to $\approx 71.4 \pm 3.1 \mu\text{m}$) after overnight shrinking at 37 °C (Figure 4A). Interestingly, these shrinking hydrogels enable the fabrication of positive features that match the optical resolution limit of the volumetric printer, and negative features also exhibit a high shrinking factor (3.1-fold). Similarly, the scaffold made with gelMA-pNIPAM hydrogel exhibited a significant enhancement of print resolution, with negative features exhibiting once more a greater shrinking ratio than positive features (3.1× vs 1.3×, respectively) (Figure 4B). While positive features (≈23%; from $\approx 59.6 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$ to $\approx 45.9 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$) did not achieve as high a resolution as silkMA-pNIPAM prints, the negative features achieved post-shrinking (≈75%; from $\approx 123.7 \pm 2.6 \mu\text{m}$ to $\approx 39.1 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{m}$) are, to date, the open channels with the smallest diameter created with a volumetric printer, highlighting the advantage of the post-printing shrinkage induced by the incorporation of NIPAM in the precursor solution, a process that does not require a change in the VP process itself. These observations open a whole range of possibilities for incorporating multiscale structures with both high-resolution positive and negative features, as well as fabrication times in the range of tens of seconds that can facilitate the creation of constructs that closely mimic the intricate micro-sized organization of native tissues.

A recent approach to enhance printing resolution in VP involves using lenses of varying magnification capabilities to reduce volumetric projection size for higher resolution features.^[50] However, this method, despite using higher magnification lenses, falls short of achieving the negative feature resolution demonstrated in our study even though resulting in an overall reduction in printable object size.^[50] Another attempt to achieve high-resolution microchannels within bulk volumetric prints utilized a sequential 2-photon ablation step, enabling the creation of 1 μm negative features.^[50] Nonetheless, the effective depth of this process was limited to 500 μm, constraining the size of modifiable volumetric prints, and the creation of intricate structures proved more time-consuming than the traditional VP approach, with even small working volumes of 0.02 mm³ taking over 10 min for full ablation.^[50]

The utilization of shrinkable bioresins, as shown in this study, offers a promising approach for achieving high-resolution features in high-speed printing. Importantly, this method requires no alterations to the optical setup of the volumetric printer and relies solely on the processing time of VP, without the need for an additional processing step.

To demonstrate the ability to create convoluted architectures consisting of complex struts and channels, and their ability to shrink into stable structures with high shape fidelity, both gelMA- and silkMA-based thermosensitive materials were used to VP

A. SilkMA-pNIPAM Volumetric printed structures

B. GelMA-pNIPAM Volumetric printed structures

Figure 4. Volumetric printing of thermally shrinkable structures. Simple VP structures consisting of positive and negative features in a pre- and post-shrinking (overnight at 37 °C) state, as well as quantitative measurements of these feature sizes made of A) silkMA-pNIPAM and B) gelMA-pNIPAM (Scale bar low magnification = 1 mm, high magnification = 200 μm).

larger, more intricate shapes. A gyroid structure, consisting of a complex network of repeating pore units, and a hollow torus knot shape with an inlet and outlet to allow perfusion were printed. For both materials, these larger, bulkier structures also underwent shrinking, at generally higher ratios than the simpler structures shown before (Figure 5). For the silkMA hydrogel, the gyroid, which represents a complex positive feature structure, underwent shrinking by a factor of 3.5 ± 0.2 , and the hollow torus knot network by a factor of 2.3 ± 0.1 , with all channels and features remaining distinct and open in the case of the channel structures (Figure 5A). The hydrogels prepared with GelMA-pNIPAM in this case, experienced a much higher shrinking ratio for both gyroid and torus knot (6.1 ± 0.5 and 5.8 ± 0.4 , respectively), indicating a more pronounced shrinking capacity of the gelatin-based material in the chosen structures (Figure 5B). This observation might be attributed to the inherent characteristics of the printing technique itself. Within the VP process, specific regions of the bioresin are exposed to light for just long enough to slightly

exceed the gelation threshold of the material. This controlled exposure prevents the polymerization of adjacent and undesired regions of the resin. As a result, the photocrosslinking of the hydrogel is halted earlier compared to the conventional casting of constructs, where the gel is allowed to polymerize fully, resulting in a higher proportion of the polymer remaining uncrosslinked under the printed conditions. After this crosslinking step, any unreacted polymer is removed through a warm PBS wash, and the resulting construct undergoes a post-curing process to complete the crosslinking, resulting in a stable hydrogel.

The observed difference in shrinking capacity could possibly be explained by taking into consideration how the volumetric printing process is done here. To obtain structures with the best possible resolution, the precursor solution is induced to physical gelation so to prevent movement in the cuvette. The gelMA is therefore left in ice prior to printing to ensure the formation of a physical gel. However, unlike gelMA, silkMA does not form a physical gel at low temperatures, hence, to ensure the presence of

A. SilkMA-pNIPAM Volumetric printed structures

B. GelMA-pNIPAM Volumetric printed structures

Figure 5. Volumetric printing of thermally shrinkable structures. Complex VP structures printed with A) silkMA-pNIPAM (top row) and B) gelMA-pNIPAM (bottom row), consisting of positive features (gyroid) and negative features (hollow torus knot) before and after shrinking (scale bar = 1 mm). * = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$.

such physical interactions, a low percentage (25 mg mL^{-1}) of non-methacrylated gelatin was added to the precursor mixture. Although no differences in shrinking were reported between gels in disk shapes containing or not containing the non-methacrylated gelatin (data not shown), the presence of this albeit low amount of gelatin could possibly both slow down the cross-linking process of silkMA and produce a slightly looser gel, facilitating greater escape of pNIPAM oligomers. As a consequence of having a decreased amount of pNIPAM present in the lattice, slightly less shrinking is observed.

It is worth mentioning that this difference was not observed in the casted gels (Figure 3).

Moreover, as can be seen from Figures S4 and S5 and the videos S1 and S2 (Supporting Information), the pores of such complex 3D structures remain open even after the shrinking process.

Overall, these data demonstrate the capability to VP intricate structures based on pNIPAM, with precise control over their volume and feature sizes through temperature adjustments. The shrinkage properties identified in this study can be precisely tailored by selecting the resin composition (whether it is slightly hydrophobic like silkMA or more hydrophilic like gelMA) and/or applying specific thermal conditions, thus enabling the creation of a diverse range of constructs suited for various applications. These findings unlock numerous possibilities for integrating multiscale structures with both finely detailed positive and negative features. Additionally, the very short fabrication times of seconds, make it feasible to produce clinically relevant-sized constructs that closely mimic the characteristics of natural tissues.

2.3. Cytocompatibility evaluation

Hydrogels prepared with pNIPAM have been extensively used in the field of tissue engineering for example for the creation of thin microgel films.^[51] These studies demonstrate the cytocompatibility of the polymer with multiple cell types, including kidney epithelial cells.^[52] Nevertheless, it is known that pNIPAM gels may contain residual monomers and impurities whose presence and release can be harmful to cells.^[53] The tolerance to these substances is dependent on the cell type and should be determined in the first place.^[54] Visual inspection showed the release of unreacted NIPAM/oligomeric pNIPAM from the gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM hydrogels during the initial hours. This was evidenced by the appearance of opalescence in the incubation liquid (water or PBS). Subsequently, the incubation liquid maintained consistent transparency, suggesting that the leakage of pNIPAM oligomers may have ceased within the first few hours (Figure S6, Supporting Information). However, the formation of an interpenetrating network between the co-crosslinked polymers could have stabilized the structure, preventing further oligomer leakage rather than merely reflecting the end of the release. To optimize the removal of NIPAM and short pNIPAM oligomers, hydrogels (including discs and printed structures) underwent dialysis in PBS for a minimum duration of 24 h prior to cell culture.

We evaluated the cytocompatibility of the different shrinkable hydrogel formulations by assessing the metabolic activity of conditionally immortalized proximal tubule epithelial cells (ciPTECs) grown on the surface of hydrogel discs (Figure 6A)

Figure 6. Establishing the PT culture on the gels and convoluted structures. A) Schematic representation of the cell seeding process on disk-shaped hydrogels. B) Metabolic activity of the ciPTECs grown on hydrogels for key time points (4 h, 1 day, 7 days, and 14 days) expressed as a percentage over cells grown on traditional cell culture plates (CTRL) and normalized to the amount of protein. C) Schematic representation of the cell seeding process in the volumetrically printed channels. D) Besides being metabolically active, live/dead staining (calcein-AM (green)/EthD-2 (red) shows differences in cell growth depending on the material combination over 14 days of culture. Front (D-E) and side F, G) views of the volumetrically printed GelMa-pNIPAM constructs as they are designed in 3D and containing a ciPTEC cell monolayer in both channels. H) Longitudinal section of the VBP construct showing the open lumens for the central channel and the coils. The depth of the imaging is limited by the cloudiness of the gels when shrunken. I) 3D rendering of the images shows open lumens for the outer spiral and the central straight channel are stable and maintained upon cell culture. L) Plot of the inner diameters of the channels as modeled and after the shrinking and cell culture. (Scale bars = 200 μm). (** = $p < 0.01$).

compared to the traditional culture (2D plastic). The groups containing gelMA (gelMA and gelMA-pNIPAM) performed superiorly compared to the silkMA-containing hydrogels, with a continuous increase in metabolic activity. In the case of gelMA, as expected, the metabolic activity outperforms the control (2.8-fold over 2D plastic at day 14), since the aqueous environment of the gelMA hydrogel has been widely shown to be a more favorable habitat for cell growth than just the plastic of multi-wells.^[55] This result aligns with previous studies on the use of gelMA in creating cytocompatible scaffolds for various cell types, including kidney epithelial cells.^[52,56]

The introduction of pNIPAM into the gelMA formulation appears to have a nuanced impact. While at day 14 the metabolic activity is still higher than the control, the increase is less pronounced than for non-thermosensitive gelMA hydrogels, which

can potentially be attributed to the reduced number of RGD domains compared to gelMA-only samples. The presence of these domains is critical for cell adhesion, and the lower number of anchoring points due to the partial replacement of gelMA by pNIPAM may explain the decreased metabolic activity when compared with gelMA alone. This finding is consistent with the idea that the specific properties of hydrogel components, such as the presence and abundance of bioactive sequences like RGD domains, play a crucial role in cell-hydrogel interactions and can ultimately affect metabolic activity.^[57,58] Cells grown on silkMA, on the other hand, exhibit only moderate metabolic activity and are characterized by fluctuations in cell behavior over time. This could be attributed to the absence of RGD domains in silk fibroin, which, as mentioned, are essential for facilitating cell adhesion and proliferation.^[59]

Surprisingly, the combination of silkMA and pNIPAM, which is more hydrophobic above the LCST of PNIPAM, appears to enhance cytocompatibility when compared to silkMA alone. However, the cells are less viable than the control materials, with values $\approx 50\%$ – 70% .

Thus, these findings emphasize the importance of understanding the interplay between specific hydrogel components and their cytocompatibility. GelMA demonstrates excellent cytocompatibility, while the presence of pNIPAM, can impact cell behavior due to the reduced number of cells anchoring sites. SilkMA alone has limitations in promoting cell viability likely due to its lack of RGD domains, but remarkably the combination of silkMA with pNIPAM can enhance cell attachment to a reasonable extent.

Together with the metabolic activity, cell-hydrogel interactions were examined by live/dead staining (Calcein-AM/EthD-2) at different time points. The results on cytocompatibility correspond with the data obtained for the metabolic activity. Over time, the gelMA and gelMA-pNIPAM formulations were able to sustain cell growth, while cells detached from silkMA gels and formed clumps in the silkMA-pNIPAM ones.

2.4. Printing a convoluted model of the Proximal Tubule

Strategies for advancing the development of the proximal tubule replicates have mainly been focused on scaffolds^[60] and 3D-printed hydrogel microfibers^[61,62] or channels.^[12] These studies highlight the importance of replicating a tube-like shape for fine-tuning cell arrangement and function.

As a proof of concept for the next generation of PT replicates, volumetrically printed shrinkable constructs containing 2 hollow perfusable channels (central straight $\varnothing = 500 \mu\text{m}$ and outer spiral $\varnothing = 750 \mu\text{m}$) were printed in gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM. In Figure 6C–E, ciPTECs were seeded in the channels of gelMA-pNIPAM constructs, until forming a monolayer and imaged with confocal microscopy. Figure 6D–G shows side-to-side the computer designs (CAD) of the prints and the images of cell nuclei (DAPI, blue) and actin filaments (F-actin, red). Similarly to the hydrogel disks, the cells were able to attach to the lumens of the straight and coiled channels and started to cover them establishing a cell layer. It is noteworthy to mention that thermally shrunken hydrogels are slightly opaque (Figure 6H), hindering the acquisition of clear (confocal) fluorescent microscopy images by limiting the penetration depth of the excitation light beam. This effect is even more pronounced in the silkMA-pNIPAM gel, which hampered acquisition (Figure S7, Supporting Information). In accordance with previous results, the negative features (i.e. the channel diameters) are maintained as the channels are visibly open (Figure 6H–L). However, the shrinking ratio (3.1 ± 0.3) was more moderate than in the cell-free counterparts (Figure 6I). We hypothesize that these differences are not due to the presence of cells, but to the different handling of the constructs when cells are included. Cell feeding carries temperature-changing steps which could have influenced the final dimensions of the construct.

3. Conclusion

This study introduced a simple and effective method to create stable tubular structures with dimensions close to those found in the human body. Our approach offers several advantages, including the ability to seed cells into tubes before shrinking and easing handling. Volumetric printing allows for flexible geometry design not possible with other methods. Additionally, our hydrogel formulation, which combined methacrylate biopolymers with NIPAM, results in a versatile material capable of shrinking at 37°C . We systematically investigated the shrinking behavior and gelation kinetics of gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM shrinkable hydrogels, observing how both could be tailored to achieve controlled shrinking at 33 and 37°C . We illustrated how the shrinking process induced a stiffening effect in the hydrogels, resulting in a proportional increase in the compressive modulus with the degree of gel shrinking. Our findings demonstrated that the integration of these shrinkable hydrogels with VP significantly enhanced the resolution of both positive and negative features. This improvement facilitated the fabrication of microchannels and intricate structures, approaching dimensions comparable to the kidney proximal tubule.

A crucial aspect of our study involved evaluating the cytocompatibility of these hydrogels, revealing noteworthy disparities when culturing ciPTECs cells on the respective materials. While gelMA-pNIPAM hydrogels exhibited superior cytocompatibility, sustaining a continuous increase in metabolic activity and maintaining cell adhesion and viability, silkMA-pNIPAM hydrogels displayed moderate metabolic activity and significant fluctuations, with cells often detaching and forming clumps. These observations underscore the impact of material composition on cell-hydrogel interactions and highlight the potential for further optimizing silkMA-based materials to improve cell adhesion and proliferation.

4. Experimental section

Materials were used as purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands) unless mentioned otherwise.

Gelatin Methacryloyl (gelMA) Synthesis: Synthesis of gelMA was performed according to previously reported procedures.^[63] Briefly, 10 g of porcine skin type A gelatin (≈ 300 bloom) was dissolved in 100 mL of phosphate-buffered saline solution (1x PBS) (pH 7.4) at 50°C for 1 h. Methacrylic anhydride (MA) was added dropwise in a 0.8 mL gram^{-1} ratio of MA to gelatin and left to stir for 2 h at 50°C . Upon completion, the solution was diluted with PBS to a concentration of 200 mL gram^{-1} gelatin followed by dialysis (MWCO: 12–15 kDa, Spectrum Lab Inc.) against deionized water at 40°C for 5 days. Lyophilization resulted in a white powder.

Methacrylate Silk Fibroin (silkMA) Synthesis: Silk degumming was based on the protocol by Rockwood et al.^[64] and silk fibroin (SF) methacrylation was based on protocol by Kim et al.^[64] Briefly, *Bombyx Mori* silk cocoons (Evrosilk, Czech Republic) were cut using scissors and the silkworm was disposed of. A $0.02 \text{ M Na}_2\text{CO}_3$ solution was brought to a boil and 5 g of clean, cut-open cocoons were boiled for exactly 5 min to remove the sericine layer. The degummed SF fibers were rinsed in cold deionized water and dried on aluminum foil overnight. SF (5 g) was then dissolved in 9.3 M LiBr (Acros Organics) at 60°C . After 1-h glycidyl methacrylate (1.12 g, 7.9 mmol) was added and the solution was left to stir for 3 h. SilkMA was purified by dialysis against deionized water for 3 days using cellulose dialysis tubes (MWCO 3.5 kDa, Sigma Aldrich) at 4°C . The dialyzed solution was centrifuged to remove impurities and stored as a liquid solution at 4°C .

GelMA and silkMA Characterization: GelMA and silkMA were characterized with $^1\text{H-NMR}$ in D_2O using an Agilent Technologies 400MR spectrometer. Data analysis was performed with MestReNova Software (version 12.0.0-20080). All peaks were referred to as the solvent peak (D_2O : $\delta = 4.80$ ppm). Determination of gelMA and silkMA methacrylation was done using an external standard (sodium trimethylsilylpropanesulfonate (DSS)) (Figure S1, Supporting Information).

Preparation of gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM Hydrogels: GelMA stock solution of 10% w/v was dissolved in PBS at 50 °C for an hour and stored at 4 °C. NIPAM stock solutions of 10% (w/v) in PBS were prepared and stored at 4 °C. To reach a concentration of 10% w/v, SilkMA was dialyzed overnight against a 40% w/v polyethylene glycol (PEG) (6 kDa) aqueous solution using cellulose dialysis tubes (MWCO 3.5 kDa, Sigma Aldrich). The concentrated silkMA solution was stored at 4 °C for no more than one week.

GelMA or silkMA stock solutions were combined with NIPAM stock solution in different ratios (1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, and 1:5) to obtain a final concentration of 10% wt/v of polymer mix. However, the 1:4 ratio (2% w/v gelMA or silkMA and 8% w/v NIPAM) was chosen for further experiments since the higher shrinking capacity was reported, and a 0.1% w/v of lithium phenyl 2-4-6-trimethylbenzoyl phosphinate (LAP) (TCI chemicals, Hong Kong) was used as photo-initiator to produce a pre-gel solution.

Pre-gel solutions were cast in open-topped cylindrical molds (1 × 8 or 3 × 8 mm). The molds were placed under Bluepoint 4 UV lamp (Honle UV technology AG, Germany) and irradiated for 40 s at a 5 cm distance (light intensity ≈ 390 mW at the light source). Crosslinking kinetics were evaluated with a Discovery HR-2 Rheometer (TA Instruments, Etten-Leur, The Netherlands) equipped with a light guide attached to a BluePoint 4 lamp (Honle UV technology) using a 20 mm plate-plate geometry. Time sweeps were performed for 5 min at 10% strain and 1 Hz angular frequency at 25 °C, the lamp was switched on after 1 min for 30 s. Data were processed with TRIOS software (version 5.0). (gelMA-NIPAM and silkMA-NIPAM refer to the hydrogel precursor solution, while gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM refer to the hydrogels).

Hydrogel Shrinking Kinetics: Hydrogel disks ($d = 8$ mm, $h = 2$ mm, ≈ 100 μL) were prepared as described before in a 1:4 gelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM ratios. Hydrogels were placed in 12 multi-well plates with 4 ml of PBS and incubated at 33 and 37 °C. Photos were taken at precisely timed time points from the moment the hydrogel was added to the warm PBS (33 and 37 °C) and images were analyzed using ImageJ software (1.53e, National Institute of Health, USA).

To estimate the amount of water expelled, a few assumptions were made: 1) uniform shrinking across all dimensions (as observed experimentally), 2) equal polymer and water density (for simplicity of the calculation; the exact polymer density was not known), and 3) complete polymerization of NIPAM monomers in the gel. Knowing the initial polymer concentration and the mass of polymer in each gel (≈ 0.015 g if all the NIPAM has polymerized), the amount of water inside the gel (at a given temperature) can be calculated using the equation:

$$\text{Water Content [\%]} = \frac{\text{Volume of the gel [cm}^3\text{]} - \text{amount of polymer [g]}}{\text{Volume of the gel [cm}^3\text{]}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Measurements of Mechanical Properties: Hydrogel disks ($d = 8$ mm, $h = 3$ mm, ≈ 150 μL) were prepared as mentioned before. Rheological properties were determined using a Discovery HR-2 Rheometer (TA Instruments, Etten-Leur, The Netherlands) with a Peltier plate for temperature control and solvent trap to prevent evaporation. All samples were measured using a plate-plate geometry (aluminum, 20 mm diameter). Data were processed with TRIOS software (version 5.0). Oscillation amplitude sweeps were performed to determine the appropriate strain for oscillation frequency sweep. Oscillation frequency sweep (strain 10%, frequency 0.1 to 100 Hz) was performed at 25 °C, 33 and 37 °C (Figure S2, Supporting Information).

Compression tests were performed in triplicates on a 2980 DMA (Q800, TA Instruments, the Netherlands), using an immersion clamp. The immersion clamp was filled with PBS at the needed temperature. Compression tests were performed using a three-step protocol: equilibration 25 °C (or

33 or 37 °C), isothermal for 3 min, compressive force ramp 2 N min^{-1} up to 5 N. From the obtained data the young modulus was calculated as the slope of σ/ϵ up to 20%.

Volumetric Printing: GelMA-NIPAM (2% w/v and 8% w/v respectively) and silkMA-NIPAM (2% w/v and 8% w/v respectively) precursor solutions supplemented with 0.1% w/v LAP were dispensed into cylindrical borosilicate glass vials ($d = 10$ mm), which were then loaded into a commercial volumetric 3D printer (Tomolite V1, Readily3D, Switzerland) equipped with a 405 nm laser, set to deliver an average light intensity of 10.13 mW cm^{-2} within the printing volume. Prior to printing, the samples were cooled to 4 °C to achieve physical gelation of the resins. In the case of silkMA, which does not thermally gelate, 1% w/v porcine gelatin (25 mg mL^{-1} ; porcine skin type A gelatin (≈ 300 bloom)) was added to the final resin blend to allow for thermal gelation to occur pre-printing and prevent artifacts due to sedimentation of the polymerized structure over time. Custom-designed STL files were loaded into the printer software (Apparite, Readily3D, Switzerland). After the printing process, the vials were heated to 30 °C to melt the unpolymerized resin and washed gently with PBS to retrieve the prints. To ensure homogenous crosslinking, the samples were submerged in 0.1% w/v solution of LAP in PBS and irradiated for 5 min in a CL-1000 Ultraviolet Crosslinker ($\lambda = 365$ nm; UVP, USA). Afterward, samples were submerged in PBS and incubated at 37 °C overnight to induce shrinking. To analyze the print resolution achievable pre- and post-shrinking, an Olympus SZ61 stereomicroscope coupled with an Olympus DP70 digital camera (Olympus Soft Imaging Solutions GmbH, The Netherlands) was used to image the printed structures, which were stained using Alcian Blue solution for better visualization. To visualize the complex prints in 3D, samples were imaged using a custom-built light-sheet microscope. All images were processed, for feature and volume measurements, as well as generation of 3D renderings of light-sheet scans, using the image analysis software Fiji.^[65]

Cell Culture: Conditionally immortalized proximal tubule epithelial cells (ciPTEC 14.4), originally isolated from human urine and immortalized as previously described,^[66] were obtained from Cell4Pharma (Oss, The Netherlands). Cells were cultured in PTEC culture medium and passaged as described by Jansen et al.,^[67] at 33 °C and 5% (v/v) CO_2 up to 90% confluency to maintain a cell proliferation state. For maturation, ciPTECs were transferred to 37 °C for 7 days prior to experimental readout.

Hydrogel Disk Casting and Preparation for Cell Seeding: Hydrogel disks were prepared as described before and transferred to a sterile low adhesion 48 well plate (Corning Costar, Sigma Aldrich). For sterilization, disks were exposed to 30 min of UV light and incubated overnight at 33 °C in HBSS supplemented with 5% P/S. A single additional HBSS rinse was performed before cell seeding to remove any residual material and kept at 33 °C to maintain the semi-shrunken stage. For cell seeding on the disks, ciPTECs were harvested with accutase, and 250,000 cells were seeded per well. After the seeding, cell-loaded disks were cultured for 7 days at 33 °C and 7 extra days at 37 °C to allow full maturation of the ciPTECs. For each experiment $n = 3$ gels were used per gel formulation. Three independent rounds were performed.

Cell Viability: The cytocompatibility of the hydrogels was characterized indirectly by measuring the metabolic activity at multiple time points post-seeding (4 h and on days 1, 7, and 14) using the PrestoBlue reagent (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Paisley, UK). Briefly, gels were washed 3 times with HBSS and incubated with PrestoBlue working solution for 1 h at 37 °C. Following incubation, 200 μL of supernatant was transferred to a 96-well plate and fluorescence was measured using a GloMax Discover microplate reader (ex. 520, em. 580–640 nm).

Cytocompatibility data was normalized by protein quantification (Pierce BCA Protein Assay Kit, Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Paisley, UK). After PrestoBlue sampling, disks were washed 3 times with HBSS. 100 μL of lysis buffer (RIPA Lysis and Extraction Buffer, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Paisley, UK) was added to the disks and thoroughly mixed. Protein quantification assay was carried out according to manufacturer's instructions and absorbance was read at 560 nm.

Cell Seeding of Volumetrically Printed Coils: GelMA-pNIPAM and silkMA-pNIPAM coils were printed as described above. The constructs were a rectangular prism (10 mm depth × 4 mm width × 4 mm length)

with an inner coiled channel of 750 μm in diameter and a straight channel of 500 μm in diameter. Immediately after the printing and similarly to the hydrogel disks, samples were sterilized for 30 min under UV light and rinsed once with HBSS supplemented with 5% P/S. The coiled channels were manually seeded with 40 μL cell suspension (1×10^7 cells mL^{-1}). For a better visualization of the filling of the coiled channels, the cell suspension was colored with an inert alimentary food dye which has been proven not to interfere with ciPTEC cell viability.^[62] Seeded constructs were cultured for 7 days at 33 °C and 7 extra days at 37 °C to allow full maturation of the ciPTECs.

Immunocytochemistry: Volumetrically printed coiled channels seeded with ciPTEC were fixed for 30 min with 4% v/v paraformaldehyde (Pierce, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) in PBS and permeabilized with 0.3% v/v triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA) in PBS for 30 min. Subsequently, the cells were exposed to the blocking buffer consisting of 2% v/v FBS, 0.5% w/v bovine serum albumin (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA) and 0.1% v/v Tween-20 (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA) in PBS for 60 min. Actin filaments were stained with AlexaFluor 647 Phalloidin (A22283, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) diluted 1:1000 in blocking buffer overnight and nuclei with DAPI diluted 1:1000 in blocking buffer for 8 min. Images were taken with a confocal microscope (Leica TCS SP8X) and software Leica Application Suite X. Images were analyzed using ImageJ. Images were converted to eight-bit, Z-projections were made, and the same threshold was applied for every image. Imaging was performed at 37 °C to prevent the swelling of the samples.

Statistical Analysis: GraphPad PRISM v.9.4.1 was used for analyzing and graphing data. Mechanical data were shown as mean \pm SD, unless otherwise stated. Statistical significance was tested by unpaired t-test with Welch's correction. All cell culture data were expressed as mean \pm SEM of 3 independent experiments performed, at least. For the viability assay, data were normalized for protein content and over 2D controls (100% viability). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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shrinking hydrogels, smart biomaterials, volumetric printing

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